

Friedelan-3 β -ol: White solid (150 mg) obtained from benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) fraction on crystallisation gave shining flakes, m.p. 276°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3480 (OH), 1450, 1360 and 1050 cm^{-1} ; M^+ , 428, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}$; acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$), m.p. 290-291° (lit.⁴, 292-294°); identified as friedelan-3 β -ol by comparing with an authentic sample.

Clerodolone: Methanolic extract of each plant gave clerodolone, as white granules on cooling. Repeated crystallisation with methanol gave colourless needles (50 mg), m.p. 288-89°; gave positive Liebermann-Burchard and INM tests indicating unsaturated nature; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3550 (OH), 1690, 1645 and 860 cm^{-1} ; M^+ , 456; confirmed by comparing with an authentic sample.

n-Triacontane and β -amyrin were also identified by comparing with an authentic sample.

Chromatographic fractionation of the aerial parts of the *C. neutens* afforded the following compounds. Fraction 1 (petrol- C_6H_6 , 1:1) afforded (24s)ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol; while β -sitosterol was obtained from the C_6H_6 fraction. Stigmasterol was collected from Fraction 4 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 - \text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, 9:1), and Fraction 5 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 - \text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, 1:1) gave clerosterol.

Clerosterol: White solid (100 mg) obtained from the benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) fraction on crystallisation yielded white needles, m.p. 146-47°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3450-3230 (OH), 1640, 960 and 890 cm^{-1} ; M^+ , 412, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2$; responded to TNM and Liebermann-Burchard colour tests; acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$), m.p. 140° (lit.⁶, m.p. 142°).

β -Sitosterol and stigmasterol were identified by comparing with an authentic sample.

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Biflavones from *Juniperus indica* (Syn. *J. pseudosabina*)

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A number of *Juniperus* species¹⁻⁷ have been examined for biflavonoids but no work has been reported so far on *Juniperus indica* (Syn. *J. Pseudosabina*). The plant leaves were chemically examined and found to contain six biflavones, two of them being minor could only be detected.

Experimental

Acetone extracts of dry leaves (3 kg) collected from Royal Botanical Garden, Godawari, Lalitpur, Nepal, after the usual purification by solvent treatment and column chromatography (Si-gel) were separated into three flavonoid fractions, I (Rf 0.16), II (Rf 0.37) and III (Rf 0.54) by preparative tlc (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36:9:5). Fraction I was found to be the mixture of two biflavones (tlc of the methylated product). It was subjected to CCD separation between MeCOEt and borate buffer (pH 9.8) which yielded compounds A and B. These were characterised as amentoflavone and cupressuflavone, respectively by comparison of m.p., m. m.p., chromatographic and pmr data of their methyl ethers and acetates with those of authentic samples^{8,9}. Fraction II on methylation ($\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{K}_2\text{SO}_3$) gave three methyl ethers on tlc, corresponding to amentoflavone and cupressuflavone hexamethyl ethers and hinokiflavone pentamethyl ether (Rf and shade in uv light)¹⁰. Fraction II was further separated into two fractions by subjecting it to column chromatography. The first fraction (minor) was found to be a mixture of two biflavones (tlc of the methylated product), identified as monomethyl ethers of amentoflavone and cupressuflavone by comparison of Rf and shade in uv light with authentic samples. The second fraction crystallised from methanol as yellow cubes, m.p. 344°, gave a methyl ether ($\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3$), m.p. 262°, and an acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$), m.p. 239°, was characterised as hinokiflavone by comparison of Rf, m.p. and pmr data with authentic samples¹¹. Fraction III crystallised from methanol as yellow cubes, m.p. 315°, on methylation and crystallisation ($\text{CHCl}_3 - \text{MeOH}$) yielded yellow needles, m.p. 262°. Acetylation ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$) provided an acetate as yellow needles ($\text{CHCl}_3 - \text{MeOH}$), m.p. 214°. It was characterised as isocryptomerin by pmr spectral studies of its acetate and also by comparison of Rf, m.p. and shade in uv light with authentic samples¹¹.

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Chemistry of Euphorbiaceae. Part-III†.
Isolation of Lupane Group of Triterpenes
from *Givotia rottleriformis* Griff.

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GIVOTIA *rottleriformis* Griff. (N.O. Euphorbiaceae) is a moderate-sized tree found in the Deccan forests. The wood is used locally for making painted toys¹. Literature survey has shown that this plant has not been examined for its crystalline principles. The bark has been examined in the present investigation.

The ether-extract of the bark furnished a brownish yellow solid (3%). It was fractionated into acidic (2.5%) and neutral (0.5%) fractions with 10% NaOH solution.

The acidic fraction was homogeneous on tlc and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 298-300°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +5^\circ$; δ 4.7 (2H, isopropylidene); m/z 446 (C₃₀H₄₈O₈). It was identified as betulinic acid by comparison of the compound, methyl ester (CH₃N₃, m.p. 220-22°) and acetate (Py-Ac₂O, m.p. 290-95°) with authentic sample of betulinic acid, methyl betulinatate and acetyl betulinic acid².

The neutral fraction is not homogeneous on tlc and showed two spots. It was adsorbed on a column of silica gel (< 200 mesh) and eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1, 2 dm³) and benzene (2 dm³)

successively. The petroleum ether-benzene eluate furnished lupeol (0.05%), m.p. 210-12°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +24^\circ$; δ 4.75 (2H, isopropylidene). The identity was confirmed by comparison with authentic sample³ (ir and co-tlc).

The benzene eluate furnished betulin (0.35%), m.p. 250-52°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +19^\circ$; δ 4.70 (2H, isopropylidene). The identity was confirmed by comparison with authentic sample³ (ir and co-tlc).

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Chemical Components of *Rhamnus virgata*

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EARLIER investigation¹ on *Rhamnus virgata* (Syn. *R. dahuricus*) of Rhamnaceae family has shown the presence of rhamnocitrin and rhamnazin. Since no extensive work has been carried out on *R. virgata*, we undertook its chemical examination for studying the phenolic components.

Stems (3 kg) of *R. virgata* from Solan, Himachal Pradesh (India) were extracted with hot ethanol and the extractives were chromatographed over silica gel. Elutions with petroleum ether to ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 4) afforded eight compounds. Of these, five have been characterised as chrysophanol, physcion, rhamnocitrin, kaempferol and 3-*o*-methylquercetin on the basis of spectral properties and direct comparisons. The remaining three are rare metabolites and have been labelled as A, B and C.

Compound A: It crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene, m.p. 186-188°. Its acetate was prepared from Ac₂O-Py and crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 140-42°; δ (CDCl₃) 6.72 (1H, br s

† Part-II, 24-Nor-cyclolaudenol from *Euphorbia nivulata*, *Phytochemistry* communicated.

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